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A STUDY ON THE INFLUENCE OF SERVICE QUALITY ON APARTMENT SATISFACTION IN CHENNAI, TNAMIL NADU.
BALA THANDAYUTHAM .Dr.Sriitharan

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Dr.S.Pragadeswaran Dr.T.Kumar

CURRENT STATUS OF CUT FLOWER BUSINESS IN TAMILNADU
I.Balamurgan Dr.K.TamizhJyothi

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INFLUENCE OF DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS ON CONSUMER IMPULSE BUYING INTENTION TOWARDS SOCIALNETWORKING SITES
C.Magesh Dr,K.Tamizhjyothi

A STUDY ON THE AWARENESS, PRECEPTION AND SATASFACTION OF POLICY HOLDERS OF PRIVATE INSURANCE COMPANIES
C.Magesh Dr.V.K.Somasundaram

QUALITY OF WORK LIFE AMONG SOFTWARE PROFESSIONAS - AN EMPERICAL STUDY
M.K.Mohammed Shafi Dr.R.Sriitharan

STRATEGIC PLANNING IN HOSPITALS
K. Mohandevi

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SL.NO	TOPICS	PAGA NO
1	INFLUENCE OF DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS ON CONSUMER IMPULSE BUYING INTENTION TOWARDS SOCIAL NETWORKING SITES C.Magesh Dr.K.Tamizhjyothi	1-8
2	Family Work Conflict Among Police Officers - An Empirical Investigation R.Rajinikanth Dr. R. Sritharan	9-16
3	A STUDY ON THE INFLUENCE OF SERVICE QUALITY ON APARTMENT SATISFACTION IN CHENNAI, TAMILNADU. P.Balathandayutham Dr.R.Sritharan,	17 - 22
4	POSITIVE PSYCHOLOGICAL VARIABLES' EFFECT ON HOLISTIC CONFLICT MANAGEMENT Dr. S. Pragadeeswaran Dr. T.Kumar	23 -31
5	CURRENT STATUS OF CUT FLOWER BUSINESS IN TAMIL NADU L. Balamurugan Dr. K. Tamizh Jyothi	32 - 42
6	AN EMPLOYEE TURNED INTO ENTREPRENEUR Dr. Mohammed Fadi Qaddo	43 - 50
7	Pomegranate fruit and its uses for Oncology-A Small Business Perspective Dr. David Jayaseelan	51 - 56
8	STRATEGIC PLANNING IN HOSPITALS K. MOHANADEVI	57 - 60
9	A STUDY ON THE AWARENESS, PERCEPTION AND SATISFACTION OF POLICY HOLDERS OF PRIVATE INSURANCE COMPANIES S.ASAITHAMBI Dr. V.K.SOMASUNDARAM	61 - 64
10	PERFORMANCE OF INDIAN AUTOMOBILE AND TYRE INDUSTRIES IN THE GLOBALISED ERA Dr. K. Natarajan Dr. K. Soundararajan	65 - 70
11	RETIREMENT PLANNING STRATEGIES AND COMPARATIVE PRODUCTS BY VARIOUS BANKING AND INSURANCE SECTORS Dr. V. NAGAJOTH B.N. SURESH KUMAR	71 - 76
12	A STUDY ON LOAN REPAYMENT CAPACITY OF SELF HELP GROUPS AND THEIR SOCIO ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS-A SPECIAL STUDY ON SELF HELP GROUPS AT INDIAN OVERSEAS BANK, MAIN BRANCH, KANCHIPURAM S.UmaMageswari Dr.V.Gugaramanan	77 - 86
13	IMPACT OF GLOBALISATION ON HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT N.CHANDRASEKAR Dr.V.R.PALANIVELU	87 - 89
14	A study on the effectiveness of employee's performance appraisal system S. Jothibasu Dr. K. Anandanatarajan R. Rajinikanth	90 - 93
15	IMPACT OF COLOR ON MARKETING - A STUDY P.Silambarasan Dr. K. TAMIZH JYOTHI	94 -97

10. PERFORMANCE OF INDIAN AUTOMOBILE AND TYRE INDUSTRIES IN THE GLOBALISED ERA

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INTRODUCTION

Transportation industry and tyre industry go hand in hand as the two are interdependence. India is one of the few countries which has attained self-sufficiency in tyre production barring the production of few special types of vehicle tyres, air-craft tyres, and snow tyres. India has constantly been exporting tyres to almost 65 countries. The industry is expected to grow at an average rate of 7 percent per annum. The industry has an estimated turnover of close to Rs 43,000 crores. It is made up of 39 players with an installed capacity of 57.3mn tyres. The industry claims perceptible export market. The tyre industry in India has had a long history of over 75 years. Three major multinationals, Firestone, Good year, and Dunlop, have been operating for a long time. Later came in CEAT. During 1960's and 1970's the dominance of the MNC's was greatly diluted with the entry of Premier. The industry was de-licensed in 1987, while permitting entry of global players under the structural adjustment programme, with ownership changes, compounded by the entry of majors; the market shares of the players have taken a new configuration. The high growth of the automobile industry has impacted the tyre industry in the recent years.

INDIAN AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY – AN OVERVIEW

The Indian Automotive Industry after de-licensing in July, 1991 has grown at spectacular rate for last few years. The industry has now attained a turnover of Rs. 1,65,000 crores and an investment of Rs. 50,000 crores. Over Rs. 35,000 crores of investment is in pipeline. The industry is providing direct and indirect employment to 1.31 crore people.

The growth in the automobile industry, consisting of commercial vehicles (CV), passenger vehicles (PV), two-wheelers (2W) and three-wheeler (3W) segments, has been slowing down. During April-July 2012, the M&HCV segment, which accounts for around 65 percent of total revenues for the tyre industry, posted a modest growth of 6.4 percent on Year-after-Year. Growth in the commercial vehicle sector is dependent on the general economic trend, development of infrastructure projects, transport economics and availability of freight, replacement period of vehicles, easy availability of credit and favourable government policies.

Today, the Indian auto components sector has over 500 organised and about 5000 unorganised sector layers. Demand from Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) account for 67 percent of sales, replacement market accounts for 19 percent, while exports account for over 14 percent. This exclusive of tyres, batteries and imported components.

A number of global automobile companies have set up their marketing hubs in India following the trend of surging demand of vehicles in the nation. With more roads being constructed and more industries being set up, the demand of the Heavy Commercial Vehicles (HCV) is supposed to grow at a very fast pace. At present, the automobile companies, like: Tata Motors, Ashok Leyland, Eicher Motors and Swaraj Mazda dominate the market of HCVs. Rapid urbanization in the various cities of the country has even increased the demand of the heavy commercial vehicles. It is believed that the auto financiers have also played a commendable role in the surging growth of domestic sale of the HCVs.

Table – 1 Auto & Tyre Industry – Performance of Key Categories percentage growth Year after Year

Vehicles	2010-11	2011-12	Apr-Oct : 2012-13 /2011-12
Medium / Heavy CV – Production	38%	11%	(-)16%
Car – Production	27%	2%	10%
Tractor Production	26%	27%	(-)8%
Tyres			Apr: 2012-13 / 2011-12 (latest available)
Truck/Bus Tyre Production	3%	3%	0.4%

Car Tyre Production	29%	4%	4%
2/3 W Tyre Production	29%	6%	(-)11%
Truck/Bus Tyre Export	(-)2%	12%	(-) 8%

Source: (Automotive Tyre Manufacturer Association) ATMA

COMMERCIAL VEHICLES Vs TRANSPORTATION

Commercial Vehicles (CVs) segment covers buses and trucks classified as medium and Heavy Commercial Vehicles (M & HCVs) and Van, station wagons and smaller weight vehicles, characterized a Light Commercial Vehicles (LCVs). Commercial vehicles' along with the railways constitute lifelines of the economy. These means of transportation deliver the goods needed by the populace besides supplying inputs to industry and other economic activities. The segment CVs supports the railway in mass transportation of people as well. Road transport scores over rail transport (both for freight and passenger) in terms of cost-flexibility trade off.

The share of road transportation has gone up from about 35 percent to 90 percent in the case of passenger traffic and from 20 percent to 70 percent in the case of goods transport. Heavy Commercial Vehicles (HCV's) transport bulk cargo over long haul (over 500km on an average). Industries like steel (secondary transport), cement (both primary and secondary transport), fast moving consumer goods (primary transport), pharmaceuticals (primary transport), oil companies (primary and secondary transport) and containerized goods are the main users. Institutionally, transport companies especially state transport undertakings, as fleet operators, are the most dominant users of HCV's. Industrial companies and large traders also own HCVs for their dedicated and captive usage.

Light commercial vehicles (LCVs) are usually referred to goods and carriage vehicles with a light capacity that varies from one region to another. The hi-growth of the LCV's segment, fuelled by the process of liberalization of the auto-industry from the regulatory controls in the wake of the setting up of Maruti Udyog, prompted the major Japanese manufacturers Mitsubishi, Mazda, Toyota, Nissan to eye the Indian market. Apart from the existing manufacturers, which had been reduced effectively to two main players in Bajaj Tempo and

Mahendra & Mahendra, new entrepreneurial activities emerged in early 1980's. The forays by Japanese majors led into the setting up of joint ventures in the LCV segment.

INDIAN TYRE INDUSTRY – AN OVERVIEW

The Indian tyre industries account for around 5 percent of the global demand as well as global supply of tyres. Domestic tyre industries have witnessed a remarkable recovery in Financial Year 2010, but it slows down in the Financial Year of 2009. This growth was driven by strong revival in automobile demand on the back of resurgence in economy, rise in employment levels, and easing of interest rate scenario. Although strong demand growth is an encouraging scenario for the domestic industry, rising imports has become key concern factor off-late. On an average, 55 percent of the production is utilised in replacement market, other 29.8 percent production is sold to OEMs directly and the remaining is exported. Not only Indian tyres are exported to more than 130 countries but three of the Indian tyre companies have gone international with manufacturing units in many parts of the world.

Table – 2 Indian Tyre Industries – At a glance

Turnover of Indian Tyre Industry	Rs. 43,000 Crores / US\$ 7.7 billion
Tyre Production (Tonnage)	15 lakh M.T.
Tyre Production- All Categories (Nos.)	2254 Lakh
Tyre Export from India (Value)	Rs. 4800 Crores / US\$ 770 million
Number of tyres companies	39
Industry concentration	10 Large tyre companies account for over 95% of total tyres production
Radialization level – current	Passenger car tyres – 98% Light Commercial Vehicles – 20% Heavy Commercial Vehicles - 18%

Source: ATMA (Financial year 2012)

ECONOMIC ACTIVITY AND AUTOMOTIVE DEMAND DRIVES TYRE DEMAND

Demand for tyres arises from three markets, namely, Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM), Replacement and Export. The demand from the Original Equipment Manufacturer market fluctuates directly in line with end-use demand for the automobile/construction equipment segment and hence is prone to a high degree of cyclicity. In contrast, the replacement market is sizeable (around 75 percent of the global sales) as well as stable. Replacement demand for tyres depends on on-road vehicle population, road conditions, vehicle scrappage rules, overloading norms, retreading intensity and miles driven; is less cyclical than Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) demand and is generally a higher-margin business for tyre manufacturers.

The outlook for the domestic automobile industry in India remains robust supported by strong GDP growth; favourable demographic profile and rising disposable income. Also, the proposed investments in roads (35,000 km of highways during FY 2008-09 – FY 2013-14; planning of over 5,184 km of National Highways and two-laning / improvement of about 4,756 km of State roads) to improve connectivity are expected to increase mileage and tyre demand over the medium term. India's growing importance as an automotive export hub for small cars is another key demand driver for tyres. In FY 2009-10, India manufactured 35.4 lakhs vehicles (29 percent growth); 105.1 lakhs two-wheelers (25 percent growth); 4.4 lakhs tractors (29 percent growth) and over 45,000 mining and construction equipment. While domestic Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) demand is expected to be robust over the medium term, the lag effect of the current phase of Original Equipment Manufacturer demand growth is expected to lead to strong, long-run replacement demand.

INDIA: THE GLOBAL AUTO HUB

The Japan External Trade Organisation (JETRO) and the Maharashtra Industrial Development Corporation (MIDC) have signed a memorandum of understanding (MoU) to set up the new industrial zone in Pune exclusively for Japanese manufacturers. India is home to 962 Japanese companies across 1,804 locations. Pune, being home to large automobile original

equipment manufacturers (OEMs), is a potential area for auto components sourcing with huge consumer market.

JBM Auto has formed a joint venture (JV) with Italian bus maker BredaMenarinibus to manufacture luxury buses in India. The Indo-Italian venture plans to set up a plant at Kosi, near Faridabad in Haryana, and produce 2,000 buses every year initially, at an investment of Rs 500 crore (US\$ 81.30 million).

Apollo Tyres Ltd has closed a deal with Japan-based Sumitomo Rubber Industries to sell its South African business for US\$ 60 million. Sumitomo will take over Apollo Tyres South Africa, including the Ladysmith passenger car tyre plant and Dunlop brand rights in 32 African countries.

CONCLUSION - The rapid improvement in infrastructure including road, port, power and world class facilities for testing and certification coupled with availability of trained manpower and enabling government policies to promote fair competition make Indian Automotive Industry and Tyre Industry more competitive in world besides making the country a favourable destination for investment by global majors in auto industry.

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